

THREAT OF RELIGIOUS EXTREMIST AND TERRORIST ORGANIZATIONS TO CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract: This article talks about the types of threats and their manifestations in the global information space today. Also, within the framework of this article, scientific and official literature is studied, and suggestions and recommendations are made regarding the existing problem.

Keywords: information security, cyberterrorist threats, modern trends, ideological battlefield, technological factors.

Missionaryism was the first of the ideological attacks that arose in the field of religion. The word missionary is derived from the Latin verb "mission", which means "to send" or "to assign a task", and "missionary" means "performer of a task". Missionary means a set of theoretical and practical activities aimed at solving defined tasks. Missionary activity is divided into "external" missions, which are defined as being carried out primarily in states, and "internal" missions, which are defined as being carried out on the territory of the state among non-religious people and people of other religions. There are many definitions of missionary in various dictionaries and sources. As almost all of them describe missionary features, this word is mainly associated with the Christian religion. For example, in the "World Book" encyclopedia, which is republished every year, it is noted that "a missionary is a person sent by a religious group to promote and introduce others to their religion." In the "Big Encyclopedia of Cyril and Methodius" published in Moscow, "missionary means the representatives of a religious association, the act of spreading one's faith among representatives of

other religions".

Missionary activities can be carried out for several purposes. For example:

-converting representatives of other nations into their religion. Through this idea, bringing people who believe in other religions into the sphere of influence of Western countries economically, politically, and spiritually;

- to create doubts among certain people about their faith and gradually lead them to abandon their faith and thus further expand their ranks.

The peak of missionary activity is proselytism. The authors of "Missionary: The Essence, Goals, Consequences and Ways of Prevention", A. Ochildiyev, and J. Najmiddinov defined the term proselytism as follows: "Proselytism directly refers to actions aimed at abandoning one's religion and accepting another religion. It is a component of missionary work in its essence." Summing up from the above, it can be said that proselytism is the result of missionary efforts. A person who accepts a religion other than his own as a result of missionary activity is called a proselyte.

One of the terms directly related to extremism is terrorism. Terrorism - (lat. fear, terror) is a method of violence based on the idea of using force and physically destroying people for certain evil goals. Attempting to impose one's judgment through intimidation and terror is characteristic of terrorism. It can be manifest in economic, political, religious, ideological, national, proud, and individual forms. Harassment, violence, subversion, and murder are common features of any form of terrorism, which is against the principles of humanism, democracy, and justice. That is why terrorism, no matter what "flag" it is carried out under, is essentially a crime against humanity, development, and goodness.

Another ideological threat in Central Asia is religious fanaticism.

Fanaticism is an attempt to blindly apply the rules and procedures formed based on a firm belief in an idea or principle and its absolutization, without taking into account other conditions, circumstances, and situations. Religious fanaticism is the actions aimed at blindly applying and absolutizing religious beliefs and rules to all spheres of social life. Fanaticism causes tensions, disputes, and conflicts between different sects in all religions, as well as in secular society. Fanatic groups do not recognize the promotion of their ideas through methods such as explanation and persuasion. They are extremely ignorant and intolerant of others in their claims. Self-righteousness, or arrogance based on the view that only I know the truth, creates violence.

Another ideological threat is "Islamophobia". According to the available information in the scientific literature, the term "Islamophobia" began to be widely used in 1997 after the publication of a report by the British researcher Runnymede Trust entitled "Islamophobia:A Challenge for All."

In general, Islamophobia refers to criticism of Islam, hatred towards it, views in the spirit of dislike, and actions based on discrimination and oppression of Muslims.

Secondly, the use of words such as "martyr", "martyr's belt", "mujahid", and "army of Allah" concerning terrorists by the mass media and official circles is also a source of misconceptions about Islam and Muslims. leading to formation.

Thirdly, the distortion of the Islamic worldview and customs is also reflected in this process.

Fighting to restore the prestige of Islam and winning is not an easy task. For this, it is necessary to develop an effective system of cooperation with all scientific institutions, religious organizations, higher educational institutions, and mass media. It is modern in creating effective ways to promote enlightened Islam

and protect it from misinterpretation. Naturally, wide use of opportunities is important.

As in all religions, Islam has been divided into different directions, sects and currents. Currently, these sects can be divided into two large groups:

- The first is the religious dogmatic sects that appeared in the early years of the history of Islam, which arose due to differences in dogmatic issues.

- The second is the religious-political sects that have developed the idea of the sects that appeared in the early years of the history of Islam and brought them into a form that meets the requirements of today's times.

The following hadith was narrated from the founder of Islam, the Prophet Muhammad, peace be upon him.

In a hadith narrated by Imam Ahmad, the Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings be upon him, said, "My Ummah will be divided into 73 sects, and all but one sect will enter hell." Then the Companions asked: O Messenger of God, which is the sect that will be saved? - when asked, our Prophet Muhammad, peace be upon him, answered: "They followed my path and that of my companions." As our Prophet reported, the Islamic community quickly split into 73 factions. To protect Muslims from false, heretical, and heretical sects, the scholars explained to them the belief of the Najiya sect that our Prophet informed them about.

Based on this hadith, Muhammad Zahid Qutqu ibn Ibrahim al-Bursawi writes the following in his work "Ahl al-Sunnat wal-Jamaat Aqeedee": "The ummah of the Prophet was divided into 73 factions, 72 factions remained astray and perished. Only the Ahl-e-Sunnah wal-Jamaat madhhab survived and was saved. This is called "literate Azam". Therefore, a person who leaves the

Ahl-e-Sunnah wal-Jamaa even a little bit has taken off Islam, that is, he has distanced himself from Islam.

According to the above hadith, the scholars agreed that the path to salvation is "Ahli sunna wal - community". Ahl al-Sunnah means those who follow the Sunnah of Muhammad, and the word "wal-jama'a" means those who follow the majority of Muslims. So, "Ahl al-Sunnah wal-Jamaa" are those who follow the Sunnah and the community. The majority of Muslims today, 92.5%, belong to the "Ahli sunna wal - community". Ahli Sunna wal-Jamaa" is shortened to "Sunni direction".

"Ahli sunna wal-jamaa" includes four jurisprudential schools and two dogmatic teachings. They include the schools of Hanafiyyah, Shafiyyah, Malikiyyah, Hanbaliyyah, and Moturudiyya and Ash'ariyyah schools.

The following are examples of religious dogmatic sects that are not part of Ahl al-Sunnah wal-Jamaa. They include Mu'taziliya, Kharijiya, Jahmiya, Azraqiya, Rafiziya, Jabariya, Qadariya and others.

Today, the forces trying to instill hatred towards Islam, religious xenophobia, and Islamophobia are developing the idea of the first ideological factions, political groups trying to create strife and corruption among Muslims, and religious extremist terrorist organizations acting under the guise of religion. Extremist organizations that belong to the group of religiopolitical factions that have been operating in the Central Asian region and are trying to increase the number of their supporters by spreading their ideas in this region include tablighists, Wahhabism, Akromism, Turkestan Islam Karakati, Hizbut-Tahrir al-Islami, Salafism, Muslim brothers, black turbans, Islamic armies, long beards, Nurchik, ISIS and others.

Islam Karimov, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in his

work entitled "Our peace and security depends on our strength, solidarity and strong will" says the following about the above-mentioned trends and actions: It is necessary to deeply instill in people's minds that the entry and spread of foreign political, religious extremism, fanaticism and other evil currents in our region poses a great threat to peace and tranquility and the future of our children. It is necessary to mobilize them to fight against evil forces by establishing and strengthening high moral and spiritual values in the thinking of our people.

Let's get acquainted with each of the above-mentioned religious extremist organizations separately. The first of the religious extremist organizations is the "propagandists". Tablighists (Arabic - to convey, that is, to convey the religious call) is a religious movement that operates under the banner of Islam but violates the foundations of Islam. The movement was founded by Muhammad Ilyas Kandekhlavi (1885 - 1944) in 1927 in the northern Indian city of Mewat.

Like other religious-extremist groups, the "Community of Tablighis" is characterized by the fact that it has a very strict hierarchical structure. At the head of the movement stands the emir (also called jimador), whose instructions are binding for all. The smallest group of preachers consists of 10 people and is headed by an emir. He is appointed on the recommendation of the board or the relevant group. The emir of the international level is appointed by the central council, which consists of the leading members of the movement. Currently, Zubayr Hassan is recognized as the head of the council. The organization of the movement in this way allows for strict control of the daily activities of each preacher and directs them to solve the set tasks.

At the first stage, preachers study the religious-confessional situation in the area they are entering, and the attitude of the government and other state bodies towards the religious. Based on the results of the study, at the next stage,

adaptation plans to the current situation will be drawn up, and efforts will be made to establish relations with local Muslim leaders. In this process, they try to present themselves as a community that does not interfere in politics and operates based on the orders of the Holy Qur'an and hadith. In the third stage, the real activities of the preachers will begin, separate groups will be formed, and efforts will be made to include local Muslims in their ranks.

The second of the religious extremist organizations is Akromiya. Akrom Yoldoshev is the founder of the "Akromiyar" group. He was educated by those who propagated the ideas of Salafism and non-sectarianism, such as Abduvali Mirzayev, and eventually became a member of "Hizbut - Tahrir", which was recognized by world scholars as a misguided sect. A. Yoldoshev, whose goal was to seek leadership and power, could not agree with the leader of "Hizb" A. Kasimov, and left "Hizbut - Tahrir". But based on his ideas, he founded his movement of "acromion". He expressed his views in the pamphlet "The Way to Faith" consisting of 12 lessons. called by name.

In addition, another religious extremist, terrorist movement is the "Islamic movement of Turkestan". Turkestan Islamic Movement: consists of thousands of militants, and hired foreign criminals. The leaders of this organization are in contact with international terrorist organizations such as "Al-Qaeda", "Taliban", "Hizbut-Tahrir", "Muslim Brotherhood", "Islamic Community" in Pakistan, separatist "Islamic Religious Movement" in the Uighur Autonomous Region of the PRC, etc. connected and expanded year by year at the expense of organizations secretly operating in Afghanistan, Turkey, Saudi Arabia and threatened the security of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan during 1997-2001.

According to information obtained from the Internet, when the leaders of "Turkistan Islamic Hararat" met with the number one terrorist Osama bin Laden,

they were given three million US dollars. This organization trained 1,500 bloodthirsty militants. The criminals had the latest weapons, including several BMPs and armored personnel carriers, and modern firearms designed to shoot down rockets.

The members of the association are in the military field camps of militants in Afghanistan, Chechnya, "Al-Qaeda", "Ansar Movement", "Islamic Party", "Jihad Movement", "Jamaat al-Tablig' wad" in Kashmir and Middle Eastern countries. 'and', trained in militarized places such as 'Favi', 'Saada', 'Miron-shokh' and 'Varsak' in the territory of Pakistan. Even today, this group is considered one of the most dangerous terrorist criminal organizations in the world.

Salafism is one of the currents that rejects religious sects and propagates bigoted views. These views are the basis of hundreds of categories today. For example, "Adolat", "Repentance", "Islamic Revival Party", and "Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan", which threatened the security and stability of Central Asia in the 90s, were created based on Salafist views. These groups propagated the ideas of "Salafism" among the population, carried out propaganda against the existing constitutional system, and aimed to seize power under the slogan of restoring the Islamic state.

All these fanatical, militant currents are mainly united by two features:

First of all, they disbelieve Muslims who do not follow their path with various excuses. They have two goals: to isolate those who join their ranks from others, that is, to isolate them, and to educate their comrades in the spirit of enmity towards others.

Second, to declare war on those who do not join their ranks. They call it Jihad in their way, but in Islam, such useless wars are called "boghai". It has nothing to do with the concept of jihad, which is used for the defense of the

country and the nation.

The above two characteristics were the characteristics of the Kharijites, the rebellious faction that first broke out from among the Muslims. Therefore, famous scientists and experts suggested that the extremist and terrorist groups, which call themselves by different names, such as "Al-Qaeda", "Turkistan Islamic Movement", "Tolitban", and "Hezbollah", are called "foreigners" under a single name. If we look at the activities of these fanatical groups, it can be seen that their subversive actions today are no different from those of foreigners who were active in the 8th century.

At the same time, the group of "long beards" can be included in the extremist currents. The members of this religious-extremist movement tried to inculcate their views mainly among the population of Tashkent city, region, and Shymkent region of the state of Kazakhstan. They believe that it is acceptable to Islamize society based on financial incentives. The actions of this criminal association were fully exposed during the investigation.

Another of the actions mentioned above is "nurchilik", and "Nurchilar" tried to operate in our country by establishing Turkish lyceums and educational centers in the 90s of the last century. The result of the goal, which seemed vague at the beginning, gradually began to be seen. Young people under the influence of "Nurchilar" began to separate themselves from other important Muslims with their views and actions. For example, excessive respect for the "nurchi" teacher who taught them, striving to follow his instructions unconditionally. , violating the fundamentals of the Hanafi school and Maturidia doctrine, which the Muslims of our country have been practicing for centuries, taking their religious views not from the scholars of the country where they live, but only from the teacher of the "Nurchi", determine the social danger of this current. gave

The Nurchik stream contradicts the Sunni direction in the following issues:

First of all, creating a separate faction that causes discord among believers is forbidden. Dividing into different groups according to the content of the Holy Qur'an and Hadith is a depraved matter.

Secondly, Said Nursi is not a mujtahid or scholar recognized by world scholars. It is not permissible to take his thoughts as a program and a slogan. On the contrary, experts have pointed out that there are contradictions and confusion in his views.

Thirdly, it is nothing but bigotry to hold back the books written only by the scholars of this nation, saying that the truth belongs only to the representatives of one nation. Because the religion of Islam commands to follow the community of Muslims, in which one nation is not seen as superior or weaker than another, and one nation is not seen as superior or weaker than another. If such a situation occurs, it is natural that many disagreements and conflicts will arise.

Fourthly, it is known that opposing the existing government and trying to take possession of it by illegal means is against the teachings of Maturidiyyah and the Hanafi school of thought. People who carry out propaganda against the existing state power belong to the "standard" group of foreigners in history; it is worth noting that they are recognized as the most harmful of foreigners.

The above examples prove that the current of "lighting" is dangerous and socially dangerous.

The largest religious extremist, terrorist organization in the history of mankind is ISIS. The Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (another name is the "Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant") was established in Iraq in 2006 under the name "Islamic State of Iraq" based on the merger of the Iraqi branch of the Al-Qaeda terrorist organization and several other terrorist groups. As the main goal,

Iraq claims to establish a single state of Sunni Muslims - a "caliphate" based on countries such as Jordan and Syria, and gradually expand it to the Middle East and North African countries.

According to information in the mass media, today, dozens of small terrorist organizations, such as ISIS, have fighters from more than 80 countries, including Central Asian republics, in the territory of Iraq and Syria.

List of used literature

1. Ochildiyev A., Najmiddinov J. Missionerlik mohiyat, maqsadlar, oqibatlari va oldini olish yo‘llari (yuz savolga yuz javob). - T.: Tashkent Islamic University publishing-printing association, 2012.
2. Xusniddinov Z. Diniy ekstremizm va terrorizmga qarshi kurashning ma’naviy-ma’rifiy asoslari. - T.: Tashkent Islamic University publishing-printing association, 2005.
3. Xusniddinov 3. Islom va mazhablar. - T.: Spirituality, 2000.
4. Shermuhamedov K., Karimov J. Islom Islom niqobi ostidagi ekstremistik va terrorchi uyushmalar (ma’lumotlar to‘plami) / Responsible editor O. Yusupov; Islamic Studies Scientific Research Center of Tashkent Islamic University.- T.: Movarounnahr, 2014.
5. Milliy istiqlol g‘oyasi: asosiy tushunchalar, tamoyillar va atamalar (qisqacha izohli lug‘at). - T.: Generation of the new age, 2002 y.
6. Tulepov A. Islom va aqidaparast oqimlar. - Toshkent.: East, 2014.

